

THE DIFFERENCES OF INDUCTIVE AND DEDUCTIVE APPROACHES IN TEACHING GRAMMAR

Sabina Istamova

Sabrina Ismatova

Navoi state pedagogical institute students

Supervisor: **Sadikova Dildora**

Abstract: The inductive and deductive approaches in grammar is that they complement each other. Both approaches are valuable for mastering grammar, as they offer different perspectives and reinforce understanding in different ways. This article provides information on experiment of the efficacy of teaching grammar in English using both deductive and inductive methods. In order to provide answers to the following questions, the inquiry also looks at which of these two approaches has beneficial impact on the academic achievement of students in grammar. What is the difference between inductive and deductive teaching of grammar? What are the advantages and disadvantages deductive teaching methods? Explanation inductive and deductive approaches with examples. At the end of the treatment period, students demonstrate several methods in practice.

Key words: Inductive approach, deductive approach, teaching grammar, positive and negative aspects

Annotatsiya: Grammatikada asosiysi induktiv va deduktiv yondashuvlar bir-birini to'ldirishidir. Har ikkala yondashuv ham grammatikani o'zlashtirish uchun qimmatlidir, chunki ular turli nuqtai nazarlarni taklif qiladi va tushunishni turli yo'llar bilan mustahkamlaydi. Ushbu maqolada deduktiv va induktiv usullardan foydalangan holda ingliz tilida grammatikani o'rgatish samadorligi bo'yicha eksperiment haqida ma'lumot berilgan. Quyidagi savollarga javob berish mobaynida ushbu ikki yondashuvdan qaysi biri o'quvchilarning grammatika bo'yicha o'quv jarayoniga foydali ta'sir ko'rsatishi ko'rib chiqiladi. Grammatikani induktiv va deduktiv o'qitish o'rtasidagi farq nima? Deduktiv va induktiv o'qitish usullarining afzalliklari va kamchiliklari qanday? Induktiv va deduktiv yondashuvlarni misollarda ko'rib chiqish. Jarayon oxirida talabalar bir nechta usullarni amalda ko'rsatadilar.

Kalit so'zlar: Induktiv yondashuv, deduktiv yondashuv, grammatika o'rganish, ijobiy va salbiy tomonlari.

Аннотация: Индуктивный и дедуктивный подходы в грамматике заключаются в том, что они дополняют друг друга. Оба подхода ценны для овладения грамматикой, поскольку они предлагают разные точки зрения и по-разному закрепляют понимание. В данной статье представлена информация об эксперименте по изучению эффективности преподавания грамматики на

английском языке с использованием как дедуктивных, так и индуктивных методов. Чтобы дать ответы на следующие вопросы, в ходе исследования также рассматривается, какой из этих двух подходов оказывает благотворное влияние на академическую успеваемость учащихся по грамматике. В чем разница между индуктивным и дедуктивным обучением грамматике? В чем преимущества и недостатки дедуктивных методов обучения? Объяснение индуктивного и дедуктивного подходов на примерах. По окончании периода обучения студенты демонстрируют на практике несколько методов.

Ключевые слова: Индуктивный подход, дедуктивный подход, обучение грамматике, положительные и отрицательные стороны.

Introduction

The basis for our capacity for clear communication is grammar. Teachers of languages devote hours to teaching grammar because they recognize its importance. However, studying grammar typically requires a lot of time, focus, and thought and because it can be challenging to find a method of instruction that meets both the needs and expectations of the students, modern learners sometimes view grammar as uninteresting. Depending on the teaching style, students may benefit to varying degrees and have varied preferences for instruction. In this study, we examine the effects of two primary approaches to grammar instruction in an effort to offer helpful recommendations for learners. (Anastasia, Sh and Emi Nogai 2022) [1]

Additionally to being a crucial part of learning a language, grammar can be difficult for those studying a foreign language. There are two main approaches to teaching grammar: inductive and deductive, both of which have benefits. Compared to the many studies conducted abroad on these two grammar teaching methods, domestic study on the subject started somewhat later and the results are frequently inadequate. As a result, investigating grammar teaching methodologies in the current setting is essential. (Linkai Huang 2023).[2]

Some agreement exists that the most effective grammar teaching includes some deductive and inductive characteristics. (Haight, Heron and Cole 2007)[3]

Inductive Learning

Inductive learning is a machine learning technique that trains a model to produce predictions based on observations or instances. Inductive learning is the process by which the model gains information from specific examples or instances and applies it to new data to anticipate outcomes. Utilizing inductive learning, a guideline or technique is not specifically built into the model.[4] Rather, the model is skilled in identifying patterns and links within the incoming data and subsequently, make use of this the ability to forecast results from new data. Developing a model that can accurately predict the objective of later occurrences introspective education. When

learning under supervision, where the Model training is done with labeled data and inductive learning is used often collection of examples. Inductive learning is employed by several reputable popular machine learning techniques, including neural networks, k-nearest neighbors and decision trees networks. Since it permits the growth of models that can predict fresh data with accuracy, especially in cases where the fundamental trends and inductive learning is a crucial approach to machine learning.

Positive aspects:

- Inductive learning models work well with challenging, complicated and dynamic data because of their flexibility and adaptability.
- Discovering hidden relationships and patterns in data: Because inductive learning models are capable of spotting connections and patterns in data that might not be immediately obvious to humans, they are perfect fit for tasks like pattern recognition and categorization.
- Enormous datasets because inductive learning models can handle big volumes of data efficiently, they are appropriate for applications that need to process large amount of data.
- Inductive learning models work well in scenarios where the rules are not explicitly stated or known in advance, as they can learn from instances without explicit programming recognized.

Negative aspects:

- May overfit to specific data- inductive learning models that perform poorly on new data may have overfitted to a parotic training sat or have learned the noise in the data instead of the underlying patterns.
- Computationally expensive feasible- The computationally expensive nature of inductive learning models, particularly for big datasets, may limit their use in real-time applications.
- Limited interpretability. Inductive learning models can be difficult to understand making it challenging to understand how they arrive at their predictions in situations where decision-making must be clear and explicable.
- Inductive learning models are only as good as the data on which they are trained; thus, if the data is erroneous or insufficient, the model may perform poorly.

Deductive Learning

Deductive learning is a type of machine learning in which a model is constructed using a set of logical principles and stages. In deductive learning, the model is particularly intended to follow a set of norms and methods in order to make predictions based on entirely new, unexplored data. Deductive learning is widely used in rule-based systems, where domain experts precisely define the rules and processes. The model is trained to follow the principles and methods in order to make conclusions predications based on the in put data.

In contrast to inductive learning, which learns from specific examples, deductive learning starts with a set of rules and processes and then applies these rules to make predictions on incoming data. Deductive learning seeks to create a model capable of exactly adhering to a set of standards and processes in order to make predictions.[5] Deductive learning is employed by several well-known machine learning algorithms, including decision trees, rule-based systems and expert systems. Deductive learning is an important machine learning method since it allows for the creation of models capable of making precise predictions based on predefined rules and guide lined.

To make a decisions or forecasts based on the in put data, the model is taught to follow the rules and procedures. Unlike inductive learning, which takes specific examples as its starting point, deductive learning starts with set of rules and uses these rules to produce predictions on incoming data. The goal of deductive learning is to create a model that can accurately follow a set of rules and procedures in order to provide predictions.

Positive aspects:

a) More effective- Since deductive learning begins with broad concepts and applies them to particular cases, it is frequently quicker than inductive learning.

b)Deductive learning can sometimes yield more accurate findings than inductive learning since it starts with certain principles and applies to the data.

c)Deductive learning is more practical when data are sparse or challenging to collect since it requires fewer data than inductive learning.

Negative aspects:

1)The rules in existence now, which might not be sufficient or up to date, limit deductive learning

2)Complex problems without clear rules or relationships between variables, as well as unclear questions are not suitable for deductive learning.

3)Biased outcomes- The degree of deductive learning depends on the quality of the knowledge base and rules, which may introduce biases and errors into the findings.

Methods :

To put this strategy to the test in real life, we will first split the class into two groups of students. Twenty of the thirty-six students in the audience requested an inductive lesson, whereas the other sixteen selected a deductive lesson irresponsible to their request. The assignment that was assigned to the students was to explain the “past continuous” tense in both techniques. The logical approach was used before the students made the decision to teach, providing comprehensive explanations of the “past continuous” tense using sileshows and a variety of movies.

The following question was posed to the class by the pupils who opted for the inductive method; “What were you doing at 5 p.m yesterday?” The pupils were given

extensive information when structural flaws were corrected I this highly enjoyable and tempting tasks. Pupils have expressed ideas that are precise and essay to understand.

Result:

Through these pictures you can see the students' interest in inductive approach.

In deductive, you cannot involve all the students in the lesson topics and they will get bored as it mostly repeated session.

Conclusion:

“Deductive thinking exists for the human as use of logical reasonable method toward the discernment of Human Mind’s Metaphysical Nature seeking the acquisition of epistemological of the Human’s relationship with Existence. Deductive method uses the Metaphysical Mind in the use of logical reasonable thought toward the discernment of Existence. Deductive logical thinking uses reason to discern the metaphysical and *apistemological* meaning of truth.

Inductive method of thinking relies upon sense experience in cognitive order to acquire knowledge. Whatever the five senses can tell the Human will be the method used to inductively, experientially discern meaning within Existence. Whatever, the Human can smell, taste, touch, hear, see will what Existence is to the Human. Using inductive method the Human will induce into Mind in order to come to know himself and all things in his Universe.

The human first uses inductive thinking, hearing, reading, seeing information to acquire knowledge. The Human first uses inductive thinking while the Human is life experiencing his Existence to tell him about this Existence. The Human may use common sense and intuition after inductively, sense experience his Existence in

cognitive order to comprehend a plethora of information constantly, continuously being exposed to him, first, by senses experiences, then through sharing ideas and information. Using induction to first acquire meaningful knowledge, the Human will use faith in cognitive order to believe knowledge. After which, the Human may use his cognitive development, learning how to comprehend, understand, finally, logical reason the validity of all knowledge the Human may acquire”- said Paulline Schiappa.[6]

But Willam Frederick explained another idea that contradicted this idea.

“I say deductive teaching is superior to inductive teaching for the following reasons: Deductive approaches to problem solving are based more on science and objective reasoning. It’s fact based. Start with known facts and deduct conclusions that are based on those facts. Inductive method is based more on inference. That is you make observations based on some evidence and conclude something is true. It’s based on evidence but not fully tested by the scientific method”- said Willam Frederick.[7]

To sum up, inductive learning, also known as discovery learning, is a process where the learner discovers rules by observing examples. This is different from deductive learning, where students are given rules that they then need to apply.

One of the main reasons the inductive teaching technique is so popular is that it fosters student engagement, whereas the deductive method treats students as passive learners.

Reference:

[1]. Anastasia Shirav and Emi Nogai “ The effect of Deductive and Inductive Grammar instructions in communicative teaching” May 23, 2022 ISSN: 1916-4742 E-ISSN: 1916-4750

[2]. Linkai Huang “ Comparing the Deductive Methods and Inductive Methods of Grammar Teaching for Chinese Senior High School Students” 2023

[3]. Hight, C, Herron, C and Cole, S-2007 “ The effects of deductive and guided inductive instructional approaches on the learning of grammar in the elementary language college classroom” Foreign Language Annals 40, 288-309

[4,5].”Difference between Inductive and Deductive learning”

[6]. Paulline Schiappa – Five degrees five world travel in affective neuroscience, University of Steubenville, Dayton University, Fordhem University.

[7].William Frederick- Published book Author, Copywriter, Consultant (1980-present).